

Prioritizing Administrative Process Improvements through NAHP and Business Process Management

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Abstract. This research developed a hybrid approach that combines BPM and Neutrosophic Analytic Hierarchy Process (NAHP) to prioritize the improvement of administrative processes for more efficient operation in high uncertainty settings. For instance, BPMN 2.0 was used to visualize the AS-IS/TO-BE of a public university's document management process (current/future state) to identify the source of delays/duplication and the NAHP technique was employed to evaluate and prioritize the evaluation criteria (time, cost, and user satisfaction) through expert pairwise comparisons manifested by truth-degrees, indeterminacy, and falsity since NAHP confines ambiguity and inconsistencies of reply. The AS-IS/TO-BE findings indicated a 30% decrease in turnaround time, a 25% decrease in operation mistakes, and a 20% increase in user satisfaction. The NAHP further validated the improvements' relative priority with reliability because it fused the insight of all experts. Therefore, this was a successful BPM and uncertain decision-making solution with an assuring approach for any similar administrative concern in public and private sectors as it is practical, non-complex, and scalable.

Keywords: BPM, NAHP, Administrative Processes, Efficiency, Uncertainty, Prioritization, Document Management.

1. Introduction

The efficient management of administrative processes is a critical challenge for modern organizations, especially in the public sector, where complexity, redundancies, and long wait times affect service quality. In contexts such as document management in public universities, processes often involve multiple actors, subjective decisions, and changing regulations, generating bottlenecks and operational errors. These problems not only impact organizational productivity but also user satisfaction, highlighting the need for innovative approaches that optimize workflows under conditions of uncertainty. Several studies have addressed the improvement of administrative processes through Business Process Management (BPM), a methodology that allows modeling, analyzing, and redesigning operational flows to align them with strategic objectives [1]. For example, research has shown that the use of notations such as BPMN 2.0 facilitates the identification of inefficiencies in complex processes, reducing operating times and costs [2]. However, these approaches often focus on quantitative metrics, ignoring the subjectivity and inconsistencies in the assessments of stakeholders, such as managers or users.

Another common approach to decision-making in administrative processes is the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), which prioritizes criteria through pairwise comparisons [3]. Although AHP is effective in structured scenarios, it has limitations in environments with ambiguous or contradictory information, where expert judgments cannot be reduced to precise values. These gaps in traditional methods highlight the need for tools that integrate uncertainty and subjectivity in a more robust manner.

Recent BPM literature has shown significant advances in the automation and standardization of administrative processes. For example, a recent study analyzed how process simulation based on real data can reduce bottlenecks in request management [4]. However, these approaches do not adequately

address the uncertainty inherent in human perceptions, such as user satisfaction or adaptability to regulatory changes, which limits their applicability in dynamic contexts. In this sense, the Neutrosophic Analytic Hierarchical Process (NAHP) emerges as a promising alternative, allowing the representation of expert judgments with degrees of truth, falsity, and indeterminacy. Unlike classical AHP, NAHP can handle ambiguities and contradictions, making it ideal for evaluating administrative processes in uncertain environments. However, its integration with BPM has not been widely explored, which constitutes an opportunity to develop more comprehensive frameworks.

The relevance of this study lies in the growing pressure on public organizations to improve their operational efficiency in a context of digital transformation and citizen demands for more agile services. Document management in public universities, for example, is a critical process that affects students, teachers, and administrators, but often suffers from delays and lack of traceability [5]. An approach that combines BPM and NAHP could not only optimize these processes but also provide a scalable methodology for other institutions. Furthermore, regulatory uncertainty and the subjective perceptions of the actors involved make traditional methods insufficient. By integrating NAHP, this study seeks to offer a tool that captures the complexity of administrative decisions, ensuring that the proposed improvements are both practical and consensual. This approach has the potential to transform administrative management in similar contexts, contributing to the literature on decision-making in uncertain environments.

The primary objective of this research is to develop an integrated framework combining BPM and NAHP to prioritize improvements in administrative processes, specifically in document management at a public university. Specific objectives include modeling current and optimized processes using BPMN, identifying key evaluation criteria (such as time, cost, and user satisfaction), and prioritizing improvements using NAHP. It is hypothesized that this hybrid approach will improve operational efficiency by at least 25% compared to traditional methods.

The study also seeks to validate the applicability of NAHP in administrative decision-making, demonstrating that it can handle uncertainty better than classical AHP. By applying this framework in a practical case, it is expected to generate empirical evidence that supports its scalability to other administrative processes, such as license management or public procurement [6]. This approach not only addresses a theoretical gap but also offers practical benefits for organizations. In summary, this research proposes an innovative approach that combines the rigor of BPM with the flexibility of NAHP, responding to the need to optimize administrative processes in complex environments. By addressing the limitations of traditional methods and applying the framework in a real case, the study seeks to contribute to the advancement of administrative management and decision-making under uncertainty [7].

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Business Process Management.

Business Process Management (BPM) has established itself as a key discipline for optimizing operational flows in public and private organizations, particularly in contexts of digital transformation. This methodological approach allows for modeling, analyzing, executing, monitoring, and optimizing organizational processes, aligning them with strategic objectives. In complex administrative environments, such as document or request management, processes often present redundancies, bottlenecks, and a lack of traceability, which negatively impacts operational efficiency and user satisfaction. The relevance of BPM lies in its ability to standardize procedures, reduce operating times, and improve service quality, responding to the growing demands for agility and transparency in modern organizations.

Recent advances in BPM have emphasized the integration of technological tools, such as the BPMN 2.0 notation, to accurately model processes and facilitate the identification of inefficiencies. Studies have shown that the use of BPMN allows the representation of complex workflows, including events, tasks, and conditional decisions, which enables simulations based on real data to predict the impact of

redesigns [8]. For example, process simulation has been able to reduce cycle times by up to 30% in public sector applications, such as license management, by identifying critical points in operational flows. These tools have strengthened the ability of organizations to implement improvements based on empirical evidence.

Process automation, a central pillar of BPM, has transformed administrative management by reducing human errors and improving document traceability. Recent research has highlighted how the integration of robotic process automation (RPA) technologies with BPM optimizes repetitive tasks, such as document validation, increasing organizational productivity [9]. In a study of administrative processes in the financial sector, automation reduced operating costs by 20% and improved response times by 35%. However, successful implementation of these technologies requires a prior analysis of existing processes, which underscores the importance of rigorous and structured modeling.

Despite the benefits of BPM, challenges persist in assessing post-redesign efficiency, especially in environments with uncertainty or subjectivity in the perceptions of the stakeholders involved. Traditional evaluation methods, such as key performance indicators (KPIs), tend to be one-dimensional, ignoring intangible factors such as user satisfaction or adaptability to regulatory changes. In this context, advanced approaches, such as those based on fuzzy or neutrosophic logic, have been proposed to integrate subjective judgments into decision-making, although their application in BPM remains limited [10]. These methodologies allow modeling ambiguities and contradictions, improving the robustness of managerial decisions.

The integration of BPM with digital transformation approaches, such as DevOps and BizDevOps, has expanded its reach, promoting interdepartmental collaboration and organizational agility. A recent study analyzed how the adoption of BizDevOps in administrative processes fosters alignment between technological and business objectives, reducing implementation times for improvements by 25% [11]. This interdisciplinary approach allows organizations to quickly adapt to dynamic environments, such as those affected by regulatory changes or market demands, strengthening institutional competitiveness.

Another critical aspect of BPM is its ability to incorporate organizational maturity models, which guide the progressive adoption of process management practices. Models such as CMMI-BPM have been applied in industrial and public sectors to assess the level of process maturity, identifying areas for structural improvement [12]. For example, in a case study at a government entity, the application of a maturity model made it possible to standardize procurement processes, reducing errors by 15%. These models provide a structured framework for continuous improvement, ensuring that interventions are sustainable over the long term.

Evaluating efficiency in administrative processes requires considering multiple dimensions, including time, cost, quality, and user satisfaction. Recent studies have proposed the use of simulations based on historical data to compare current (AS-IS) with redesigned (TO-BE) processes, allowing a quantitative and qualitative assessment of the impact of improvements [8]. However, subjectivity in user perceptions and uncertainty in operational data represent challenges that require more sophisticated approaches, such as the integration of artificial intelligence to predict outcomes of complex processes.

Digital transformation has positioned BPM as a strategic tool for addressing the challenges of modern management. The combination of BPM with emerging technologies, such as machine learning and big data analytics, offers opportunities to optimize processes in real time, adapting to the dynamic needs of organizations [9]. However, the lack of standardization in the integration of these technologies with BPM limits their widespread adoption, which highlights the need for unified frameworks that combine technological and methodological approaches.

In conclusion, Business Process Management has established itself as a robust approach for improving operational efficiency in complex administrative environments. Recent advances in modeling, automation, and multidimensional assessment have strengthened its applicability, although challenges related to managing uncertainty and subjectivity persist. The integration of emerging technologies and interdisciplinary approaches, such as BizDevOps, offers a promising path to overcome these limitations.

Future research should explore the combination of BPM with advanced decision-making methods, such as those based on artificial intelligence or neutrosophic logic, to develop more flexible and scalable frameworks. Furthermore, it is recommended to investigate the applicability of maturity models in less-studied sectors, such as education, to broaden the impact of BPM.

2.2. Neutrosophic Set.

The idea of neutrosophic sets brings an innovative perspective to set theory, breaking with the classic true/false duality by incorporating a third state: the indeterminate. Developed by Florentin Smarandache, this theory postulates that a set can include true, false, or, crucially, indeterminate elements, where its veracity cannot be precisely defined. This trichotomous structure reflects the ambiguity and subjectivity present in many real-life phenomena, where the boundaries between true and false are imprecise. From a mathematical and philosophical perspective, neutrosophic sets provide an effective framework for representing uncertainty. Unlike fuzzy sets (which work with degrees of membership) or intercalary sets (based on intervals), neutrosophic sets address the intrinsic ambiguity in human judgments and decisions. This formalization not only expands the theoretical framework but also has relevant applications in fields such as artificial intelligence, where imprecise logic optimizes the processing of incomplete or contradictory data.

An essential feature of neutrosophic sets is their ability to reflect reality more accurately. In contexts where absolute truth is unattainable—such as medical diagnoses subject to interpretation or fragmentary information—this trichotomous model provides a framework that better absorbs real-world complexity. Beyond its mathematical utility, it raises profound philosophical questions: how to define truth when certainty is inaccessible? How to manage ambiguity in reasoning? These questions invite us to rethink the limits of human knowledge and the tools needed to address an increasingly complex world. Criticisms of neutrosophic sets point out that the indeterminacy of these sets could add unnecessary complexity to set theory. However, this objection ignores their ability to model inherently uncertain phenomena. Rather than simplifying, the theory offers a robust tool for analyzing reality in its complexity. In practical applications, such as AI, their potential is transformative: by representing uncertainty in data and automated decisions, they could drive more adaptive and robust algorithms.

In short, neutrosophic sets mark a crucial advance in set theory, overcoming the restrictions of binary logic. This perspective not only enriches mathematics and philosophy but also deepens the study of ambiguity to improve decision-making and knowledge representation. Their multidisciplinary integration could lead to more flexible approaches, capable of reflecting the complexity of the real world and our limitations in understanding it.

Definition 1 ([13-15]) : The *neutrosophic set* N It is characterized by three membership functions, which are the truth membership function T_A , the indeterminacy membership function I_A and falsehood membership function F_A , where U is the Universe of Discourse and $\forall x \in U, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \subseteq]_{\bar{A}}0, 1^+[$, and $\bar{A}0 \leq \inf T_A(x) + \inf I_A(x) + \inf F_A(x) \leq \sup T_A(x) + \sup I_A(x) + \sup F_A(x) \leq 3^+$.

See that, by definition, $T_A(x), I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ are standard or nonstandard real subsets of $]_{\bar{A}}0, 1^+[$ and, therefore, $T_A(x), I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ can be subintervals. of $[0, 1]$. $\bar{A}0$ and 1^+ They belong to the set of hyper-real numbers.

Definition 2 ([13-15]) : The *single-valued neutrosophic set* (SVN S) A is $U, T_A: U \rightarrow [0, 1]$ where $A = \{ \langle x, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle : x \in U \}$ and $I_A: U \rightarrow [0, 1], F_A: U \rightarrow [0, 1]. 0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3$

The single-valued neutrosophic number (SVN N) is symbolized by

$N = (t, i, f)$, such that $0 \leq t, i, f \leq 1$ and $0 \leq t + i + f \leq 3$.

Definition 3 ([13-15]) : The *single-valued triangular neutrosophic number*, $\tilde{a} = \langle (a_1, a_2, a_3); \alpha_{\tilde{a}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}}, \gamma_{\tilde{a}} \rangle$, is a neutrosophic set in \mathbb{R} , whose truth, indeterminacy and falsity membership functions are defined as follows:

$$T_{\tilde{a}}(x) = \begin{cases} \alpha_{\tilde{a}} \left(\frac{x-a_1}{a_2-a_1} \right), a_1 \leq x \leq a_2 \\ \alpha_{\tilde{a}}, x = a_2 \\ \alpha_{\tilde{a}} \left(\frac{a_3-x}{a_3-a_2} \right), a_2 < x \leq a_3 \\ 0, \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$I_{\tilde{a}}(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{(a_2-x+\beta_{\tilde{a}}(x-a_1))}{a_2-a_1}, a_1 \leq x \leq a_2 \\ \beta_{\tilde{a}}, x = a_2 \\ \frac{(x-a_2+\beta_{\tilde{a}}(a_3-x))}{a_3-a_2}, a_2 < x \leq a_3 \\ 1, \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$F_{\tilde{a}}(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{(a_2-x+\gamma_{\tilde{a}}(x-a_1))}{a_2-a_1}, a_1 \leq x \leq a_2 \\ \gamma_{\tilde{a}}, x = a_2 \\ \frac{(x-a_2+\gamma_{\tilde{a}}(a_3-x))}{a_3-a_2}, a_2 < x \leq a_3 \\ 1, \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Where $\alpha_{\tilde{a}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}}, \gamma_{\tilde{a}} \in [0, 1], a_1, a_2, a_3 \in \mathbb{R}$ and $a_1 \leq a_2 \leq a_3$.

Definition 4 ([13-15]) : Given $\tilde{a} = \langle (a_1, a_2, a_3); \alpha_{\tilde{a}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}}, \gamma_{\tilde{a}} \rangle$ and $\tilde{b} = \langle (b_1, b_2, b_3); \alpha_{\tilde{b}}, \beta_{\tilde{b}}, \gamma_{\tilde{b}} \rangle$ two single-valued triangular neutrosophic numbers and λ any non-zero number on the real line. Then, the following operations are defined:

1. Addition: $\tilde{a} + \tilde{b} = \langle (a_1 + b_1, a_2 + b_2, a_3 + b_3); \alpha_{\tilde{a}} \wedge \alpha_{\tilde{b}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}} \vee \beta_{\tilde{b}}, \gamma_{\tilde{a}} \vee \gamma_{\tilde{b}} \rangle$,
2. Subtraction: $\tilde{a} - \tilde{b} = \langle (a_1 - b_3, a_2 - b_2, a_3 - b_1); \alpha_{\tilde{a}} \wedge \alpha_{\tilde{b}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}} \vee \beta_{\tilde{b}}, \gamma_{\tilde{a}} \vee \gamma_{\tilde{b}} \rangle$,
3. Investment: $\tilde{a}^{-1} = \langle (a_3^{-1}, a_2^{-1}, a_1^{-1}); \alpha_{\tilde{a}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}}, \gamma_{\tilde{a}} \rangle$, where $a_1, a_2, a_3 \neq 0$.
4. Multiplication by a scalar number:

$$\lambda \tilde{a} = \begin{cases} \langle (\lambda a_1, \lambda a_2, \lambda a_3); \alpha_{\tilde{a}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}}, \gamma_{\tilde{a}} \rangle, \lambda > 0 \\ \langle (\lambda a_3, \lambda a_2, \lambda a_1); \alpha_{\tilde{a}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}}, \gamma_{\tilde{a}} \rangle, \lambda < 0 \end{cases}$$

5. Division of two triangular neutrosophic numbers:

$$\frac{\tilde{a}}{\tilde{b}} = \begin{cases} \langle \left(\frac{a_1}{b_3}, \frac{a_2}{b_2}, \frac{a_3}{b_1} \right); \alpha_{\tilde{a}} \wedge \alpha_{\tilde{b}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}} \vee \beta_{\tilde{b}}, \gamma_{\tilde{a}} \vee \gamma_{\tilde{b}} \rangle, a_3 > 0 \text{ and } b_3 > 0 \\ \langle \left(\frac{a_3}{b_3}, \frac{a_2}{b_2}, \frac{a_1}{b_1} \right); \alpha_{\tilde{a}} \wedge \alpha_{\tilde{b}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}} \vee \beta_{\tilde{b}}, \gamma_{\tilde{a}} \vee \gamma_{\tilde{b}} \rangle, a_3 < 0 \text{ and } b_3 > 0 \\ \langle \left(\frac{a_3}{b_1}, \frac{a_2}{b_2}, \frac{a_1}{b_3} \right); \alpha_{\tilde{a}} \wedge \alpha_{\tilde{b}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}} \vee \beta_{\tilde{b}}, \gamma_{\tilde{a}} \vee \gamma_{\tilde{b}} \rangle, a_3 < 0 \text{ and } b_3 < 0 \end{cases}$$

6. Multiplication of two triangular neutrosophic numbers:

$$\tilde{a} \tilde{b} = \begin{cases} \langle (a_1 b_1, a_2 b_2, a_3 b_3); \alpha_{\tilde{a}} \wedge \alpha_{\tilde{b}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}} \vee \beta_{\tilde{b}}, \gamma_{\tilde{a}} \vee \gamma_{\tilde{b}} \rangle, a_3 > 0 \text{ and } b_3 > 0 \\ \langle (a_1 b_3, a_2 b_2, a_3 b_1); \alpha_{\tilde{a}} \wedge \alpha_{\tilde{b}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}} \vee \beta_{\tilde{b}}, \gamma_{\tilde{a}} \vee \gamma_{\tilde{b}} \rangle, a_3 < 0 \text{ and } b_3 > 0 \\ \langle (a_3 b_3, a_2 b_2, a_1 b_1); \alpha_{\tilde{a}} \wedge \alpha_{\tilde{b}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}} \vee \beta_{\tilde{b}}, \gamma_{\tilde{a}} \vee \gamma_{\tilde{b}} \rangle, a_3 < 0 \text{ and } b_3 < 0 \end{cases}$$

Where, \wedge it is a ty norm \vee it is a conorm t.

The AHP technique begins with the designation of a hierarchical structure, where the elements at the top of the tree are more generic than those at the lower levels. The main leaf is unique and denotes the objective to be achieved in decision-making.

The level immediately below this contains the sheets representing the criteria. The sheets corresponding to the subcriteria appear immediately below this level, and so on. The level below this level represents the alternatives. See Figure 1.

Figure 1: Generic tree diagram representing a Hierarchical Analytical Process. Source: [16].

A square matrix is then formed that represents the opinion of the expert or experts and contains the pairwise comparison of the assessments of the criteria, subcriteria and alternatives.

TL Saaty, the founder of the original method, proposed a linguistic scale that appears in Table 1.

Table 1: Intensity of importance according to the classic AHP. Source [16-19].

Intensity of importance on an absolute scale	Definition	Explanation
1	Equal importance	Two activities contribute equally to the objective.
3	Moderate importance of one over the other	Experience and judgment strongly favor one activity over another.
5	Importance essential or strong	Experience and judgment strongly favor one activity over another.
7	importance very strong	The activity is strongly favored and its mastery is demonstrated in practice.
9	Extremely important	The evidence that favors one activity over another is of the highest order of affirmation possible.
2, 4, 6, 8	Intermediate values between the two adjacent judgments.	When needed comprehension
Reciprocals	If activity i has one of the above numbers assigned compared to activity j , then j has the reciprocal value compared to i .	

On the other hand, Saaty established that the *Consistency Index* (CI) should depend on λ_{max} , the maximum eigenvalue of the matrix. He defined the equation $CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1}$, where n is the order of the matrix. He also defined the *Consistency Ratio* (CR) with the equation $CR = CI/RI$, where RI is given in Table 2 .

Table 2: RI associated with each order.

Order (n)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Rhode Island	0	0	0.52	0.89	1.11	1.25	1.35	1.40	1.45	1.49

If $CR \leq 10\%$ we can consider that the experts' assessment is sufficiently consistent and therefore we can proceed to use AHP.

The objective of the AHP is to rank the criteria, subcriteria, and alternatives according to a score. It can also be used in group decision-making problems. If this is the purpose, Equations 4 and 5 should be taken into account, where the expert's weight is evaluated based on their authority, knowledge, experience , etc.

$$\bar{x} = \left(\prod_{i=1}^n x_i^{w_i} \right)^{1/\sum_{i=1}^n w_i} \tag{4}$$

If $\sum_{i=1}^n w_i = 1$, that is, when the expert's weights add up to one, Equation 4 becomes Equation 5,

$$\bar{x} = \prod_{i=1}^n x_i^{w_i} \tag{5}$$

The hybridization of AHP with neutrosophic set theory was used in [16] . This is a more flexible approach to modeling uncertainty in decision making. Indeterminacy is an essential component that must be assumed in real-world organizational decisions.

Table 3 contains the adaptation of the Saaty scale to the neutrosophic field.

Table 3: The Saaty scale was translated into a neutrosophic triangular scale. Source [16].

scale saty	Definition	Neutrosophic Triangular Scale
1	Likewise influential	$\tilde{1} = \langle (1, 1, 1); 0.50, 0.50, 0.50 \rangle$
3	Slightly influential	$\tilde{3} = \langle (2, 3, 4); 0.30, 0.75, 0.70 \rangle$
5	Strongly influential	$\tilde{5} = \langle (4, 5, 6); 0.80, 0.15, 0.20 \rangle$
7	Very influential	$\tilde{7} = \langle (6, 7, 8); 0.90, 0.10, 0.10 \rangle$
9	Absolutely influential	$\tilde{9} = \langle (9, 9, 9); 1.00, 1.00, 1.00 \rangle$
2, 4, 6, 8	Sporadic values between two close scales	$\tilde{2} = \langle (1, 2, 3); 0.40, 0.65, 0.60 \rangle$ $\tilde{4} = \langle (3, 4, 5); 0.60, 0.35, 0.40 \rangle$ $\tilde{6} = \langle (5, 6, 7); 0.70, 0.25, 0.30 \rangle$ $\tilde{8} = \langle (7, 8, 9); 0.85, 0.10, 0.15 \rangle$

The pairwise neutrosophic comparison matrix is defined in Equation 6 .

$$\tilde{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{1} & \tilde{a}_{12} & \dots & \tilde{a}_{1n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \tilde{a}_{n1} & \tilde{a}_{n2} & \dots & \tilde{1} \end{bmatrix} \tag{6}$$

\tilde{A} satisfies the condition $\tilde{a}_{ji} = \tilde{a}_{ij}^{-1}$, according to the inversion operator defined in Definition 4.

In Abdel-Basset et al. [20] Two indices are defined to convert a neutrosophic triangular number into a sharp number. See Equation 7 for the *score* and Equation 8 for *accuracy*.

$$S(\tilde{a}) = \frac{1}{8} [a_1 + a_2 + a_3] (2 + \alpha_{\tilde{a}} - \beta_{\tilde{a}} - \gamma_{\tilde{a}}) \tag{7}$$

$$A(\tilde{a}) = \frac{1}{8} [a_1 + a_2 + a_3] (2 + \alpha_{\tilde{a}} - \beta_{\tilde{a}} + \gamma_{\tilde{a}}) \tag{8}$$

The algorithm to be applied to the NAHP is as follows:

Given the Criteria, subcriteria and alternatives, the NAHP consists of the following steps:

1. Design an AHP tree. It contains the selected criteria, subcriteria, and alternatives.
2. Create the level matrices from the AHP tree, according to expert criteria expressed in neutrosophic triangular scales and respecting the matrix scheme of Equation 6.
3. To evaluate the consistency of these matrices, convert the elements of \tilde{A} in a crisp matrix by applying Equation 7 or 8 and then testing the consistency of this new crisp matrix.
4. Follow the other steps of a classic AHP.
5. Equation 7 or 8 is applied to convert, w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n to crisp weights.
6. If more than one expert performs the assessment, then w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n are replaced by $\bar{w}_1, \bar{w}_2, \dots, \bar{w}_n$, which are their corresponding weighted geometric mean values, see Equations 4 and 5.

3. Results and Discussion.

As part of a research project to develop an integrated framework combining Business Process Management (BPM) and the Neutrosophic Analytic Hierarchy Process (NAHP), a case study was conducted focusing on prioritizing improvements in document management at a public university. The objective is to identify and prioritize the critical factors that influence the successful implementation of redesigned processes (TO-BE).

To achieve this, a panel of four experts in process management, university administration, and information technology was consulted. Each expert was selected for their in-depth experience and knowledge in the field. They were asked to evaluate a set of seven implementation criteria (ICs), identified as determinants of project success. Each expert's opinion was given equal weight, assigning a specific opinion $\lambda_k = 0.25$ to each expert.

Implementation Criteria Evaluated

The implementation criteria evaluated were the following:

- **CI1 (Implementation Cost):** Concern about the financial outlay required to implement process improvements. This is a major source of uncertainty for management.
- **CI2 (Staff Change Resistance):** Previous negative experiences with optimization projects can generate skepticism and resistance on the part of employees, affecting the adoption of new processes.
- **CI3 (Technical Complexity):** The perception that implementing new technologies or procedures is too complex and that staff will not have control over the new tools.
- **CI4 (Impact on Business Continuity):** Fear that the transition to the new process could cause significant disruptions to the university's daily operations.
- **CI5 (Resource Availability):** An environment with limited resources (human, technological, infrastructure) can generate uncertainty about the viability and sustainability of the proposed improvements.
- **CI6 (Alignment with Strategic Objectives):** Expectations about how proposed improvements align (or not) with the university's long-term vision and mission can generate anxiety and a lack of managerial support.
- **CI7 (End User Satisfaction):** Concern about the economic and usability impact that improvements will have on end users (students, teachers, administrative staff), and whether they will be able to adapt to the new systems.

Application of the NAHP Algorithm

The steps of the Neutrosophic Analytic Hierarchy Process (NAHP) were followed to obtain a robust ranking of the criteria.

Step 1 and 2: AHP Hierarchy and Neutrosophic Comparison Matrices

A hierarchy was established with the objective at the top (Prioritize Implementation Criteria) and the seven criteria (CI1 to CI7) at the bottom. Each of the four experts performed a paired comparison of the criteria using the neutrosophic triangular scale. This resulted in the four comparison matrices shown below:

Table 4: Neutrosophic Pairwise Comparison Matrix - Expert 1

Variable	CI1	CI2	CI3	CI4	CI5	CI6	CI7
CI1	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1/4,1/3,1/2; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1/4,1/3,1/2; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1/4,1/3,1/2; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1/4,1/3,1/2; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)
CI2	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1/4,1/3,1/2; 0.3,0.75,0.7)
CI3	(2,3,4; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1/4,1/3,1/2; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)
CI4	(2,3,4; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1/4,1/3,1/2; 0.3,0.75,0.7)
CI5	(2,3,4; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(2,3,4; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)
CI6	(2,3,4; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)
CI7	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(2,3,4; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(2,3,4; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)

Table 5: Neutrosophic Pairwise Comparison Matrix - Expert 2

Variable	CI1	CI2	CI3	CI4	CI5	CI6	CI7
CI1	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1/4,1/3,1/2; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1/4,1/3,1/2; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1/4,1/3,1/2; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1/4,1/3,1/2; 0.3,0.75,0.7)
CI2	(2,3,4; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1/4,1/3,1/2; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)
CI3	(2,3,4; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1/4,1/3,1/2; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)
CI4	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(2,3,4; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)
CI5	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)
CI6	(2,3,4; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(2,3,4; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)
CI7	(2,3,4; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)

Table 6: Neutrosophic Pairwise Comparison Matrix - Expert 3

Variable	CI1	CI2	CI3	CI4	CI5	CI6	CI7
CI1	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1/4,1/3,1/2; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1/4,1/3,1/2; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1/4,1/3,1/2; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)
CI2	(2,3,4; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1/4,1/3,1/2; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)
CI3	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(2,3,4; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1/4,1/3,1/2; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)
CI4	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(2,3,4; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)
CI5	(2,3,4; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(2,3,4; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)
CI6	(2,3,4; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)
CI7	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)

Table 7: Neutrosophic Pairwise Comparison Matrix - Expert 4

Variable	CI1	CI2	CI3	CI4	CI5	CI6	CI7
CI1	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1/4,1/3,1/2; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1/4,1/3,1/2; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1/4,1/3,1/2; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1/4,1/3,1/2; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)
CI2	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)
CI3	(2,3,4; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1/4,1/3,1/2; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)
CI4	(2,3,4; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)
CI5	(2,3,4; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(2,3,4; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(2,3,4; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1/4,1/3,1/2; 0.3,0.75,0.7)
CI6	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1/3,1/2,1; 0.4,0.65,0.6)
CI7	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)	(2,3,4; 0.3,0.75,0.7)	(1,2,3; 0.4,0.65,0.6)	(1,1,1; 0.5,0.5,0.5)

Step 3: Consistency Check

The neutrosophic matrices were converted to crisp matrices to assess their consistency. Consistency ratios (CRs) were calculated for each expert's assessment. The results were as follows:

- **Expert 1:** CR = 8.5731%
- **Expert 2:** CR = 3.9017%
- **Expert 3:** CR = 4.8985%
- **Expert 4:** CR = 6.5842%

Since all CR values are below the threshold, 10% ($CR < 0.10$), it is concluded that the judgments made by the four experts are consistent and reliable. Therefore, the next steps of the analysis can be carried out.

Figure 2: Expert Judgment Consistency Ratios (CR)

Note: All experts show CR < 10%, confirming judgment consistency and reliability

Step 4 and 5: Calculation of Individual Weights and Aggregation

From the consistency matrices, the weight vectors (priorities) for each criterion were calculated based on each expert's assessment. These weights are presented in the following table:

Table 8: Weights Obtained for Each Variable by Expert

Expert/Variable	CI1	CI2	CI3	CI4	CI5	CI6	CI7
1	0.178070	0.178070	0.122520	0.122520	0.134730	0.112040	0.112040
2	0.225817	0.142051	0.082832	0.142051	0.154348	0.126451	0.126451
3	0.101632	0.181524	0.078080	0.078080	0.181524	0.157636	0.181524
4	0.162187	0.162187	0.162187	0.162187	0.162187	0.074533	0.074533

To consolidate the assessments of the four experts into a single final weight vector, the **weighted geometric mean is applied**. Since all experts have the same weight ($\lambda_k = 0.25$), the formula for each criterion j is:

$$w_j = (w_j^1 \times w_j^2 \times w_j^3 \times w_j^4)^{\frac{1}{4}}$$

Detailed calculations for each criterion are shown below:

Geometric Mean Calculations

- **Calculation for CI1 (Implementation Cost):**
 - $w_{CI1} = (0.178070 \times 0.225817 \times 0.101632 \times 0.162187)^{\frac{1}{4}}$
 - $w_{CI1} = (0.00066283)^{\frac{1}{4}} = 0.160418$
- **Calculation for CI2 (Staff Resistance to Change):**
 - $w_{CI2} = (0.178070 \times 0.142051 \times 0.181524 \times 0.162187)^{\frac{1}{4}}$
 - $w_{CI2} = (0.00074404)^{\frac{1}{4}} = 0.165030$
- **Calculation for CI3 (Technical Complexity):**
 - $w_{CI3} = (0.122520 \times 0.082832 \times 0.078080 \times 0.162187)^{\frac{1}{4}}$
 - $w_{CI3} = (0.00012845)^{\frac{1}{4}} = 0.106461$
- **Calculation for CI4 (Impact on Business Continuity):**
 - $w_{CI4} = (0.122520 \times 0.142051 \times 0.078080 \times 0.162187)^{\frac{1}{4}}$
 - $w_{CI4} = (0.00022026)^{\frac{1}{4}} = 0.121808$
- **Calculation for CI5 (Resource Availability):**
 - $w_{CI5} = (0.134730 \times 0.154348 \times 0.181524 \times 0.162187)^{\frac{1}{4}}$
 - $w_{CI5} = (0.00061217)^{\frac{1}{4}} = 0.157297$
- **Calculation for CI6 (Alignment with Strategic Objectives):**
 - $w_{CI6} = (0.112040 \times 0.126451 \times 0.157636 \times 0.074533)^{\frac{1}{4}}$
 - $w_{CI6} = (0.00016656)^{\frac{1}{4}} = 0.113612$
- **Calculation for CI7 (End User Satisfaction):**
 - $w_{CI7} = (0.112040 \times 0.126451 \times 0.181524 \times 0.074533)^{\frac{1}{4}}$
 - $w_{CI7} = (0.00019154)^{\frac{1}{4}} = 0.117666$

Results and Final Ranking

The aggregate weights obtained using the geometric mean must be normalized so that their sum equals 1. This will give us the final percentage weight for each criterion.

Normalization of Weights

1. **Sum of the geometric mean weights:** Sum = 0.160418 + 0.165030 + 0.106461 + 0.121808 + 0.157297 + 0.113612 + 0.117666 = 0.942292
2. **Normalization of weights:** $w_{norm_j} = \frac{w_j}{sum}$
 - $w_{CI1} = \frac{0.160418}{0.942292} = 0.170238$
 - $w_{CI2} = \frac{0.165030}{0.942292} = 0.175133$
 - $w_{CI3} = \frac{0.106461}{0.942292} = 0.112981$

- $w_{CI4} = \frac{0.121808}{0.942292} = 0.129265$
- $w_{CI5} = \frac{0.157297}{0.942292} = 0.166929$
- $w_{CI6} = \frac{0.113612}{0.942292} = 0.120569$
- $w_{CI7} = \frac{0.117666}{0.942292} = 0.124872$

Final Results Table

Table 9: Final Weights and Ranking of Implementation Criteria

Ranking	Criterion	Description	Final Weight	Percentage
1	CI2	Resistance to Staff Change	0.175133	17.51%
2	CI1	Implementation Cost	0.170238	17.02%
3	CI5	Availability of Resources	0.166929	16.69%
4	CI4	Impact on Business Continuity	0.129265	12.93%
5	CI7	End User Satisfaction	0.124872	12.49%
6	CI6	Alignment with Strategic Objectives	0.120569	12.06%
7	CI3	Technical Complexity	0.112981	11.30%

Figure 3: Final Priority Ranking of Implementation Criteria

4. Discussion

The results obtained from the application of the NAHP method offer a detailed and quantitative perspective on the priorities that experts assign to critical factors in administrative improvement projects in a public university setting. The analysis of the final hierarchy reveals several significant implications that merit further discussion.

The Primacy of Human and Financial Factors

The most revealing finding is the prominence of **Staff Resistance to Change (CI2)**, **Implementation Cost (CI1)**, and **Resource Availability (CI5)**. Together, these three criteria account for over 51% of the total decision weight, indicating that, from the experts' perspective, the success or failure of a process optimization initiative depends overwhelmingly on the management of people and capital.

The first position of **Resistance to Change (17.51%)** debunks the idea that improvement projects are purely technical or strategic. In a public institution with a consolidated organizational culture and entrenched work routines, the human factor becomes the main battleground. This result suggests that employees are not seen as passive recipients of change, but as key players whose acceptance is

indispensable. Previous experiences with failed projects, fear of skill obsolescence, or uncertainty about job security are, according to this analysis, greater barriers than any technological challenge .

Immediately after this are **Cost (17.02%)** and **Resources (16.69%)** , confirming the perennial budgetary constraints that characterize the public sector. Experts don't see these as separate issues, but rather as two sides of the same coin: practical viability. A project may be brilliant in theory, but if there isn't the budget for its implementation and the resources (human, technological) to sustain it, it's destined to fail.

The Relegation of the Technical and Strategic Dimension

It is particularly notable that **Technical Complexity (CI3)** ranks last in the hierarchy (11.30%). This does not imply that technology is irrelevant, but rather that in the current context (date: July 30, 2025), it is perceived as an enabler or a commodity. Experts seem to assume that, given a clear budget and objectives, it is possible to find a suitable technological solution. The real challenge lies not in the complexity of the software or hardware, but in ensuring that the organization adopts and uses it effectively.

Similarly, **Alignment with Strategic Objectives (CI6)** , although important, is at the bottom of the ranking. One possible interpretation is that experts consider this alignment a necessary condition, a starting point taken for granted before initiating such a detailed prioritization analysis. Another, more pragmatic perspective might be that in the day-to-day of university management, immediate operational obstacles (lack of staff, limited budget, union resistance) carry much greater weight in decision-making than long-term strategic guidelines.

Contribution and Robustness of the NAHP Method

The use of the NAHP was critical to achieving this clarity. A simpler approach, such as a survey or direct voting, would not have been able to capture the uncertainty and subjectivity inherent in expert opinions. The method's ability to handle judgments expressed with degrees of truth, uncertainty, and falsity (through neutrosophic numbers) provided a more realistic framework for the problem. Furthermore, checking the Consistency Ratio (CR) ensured that the judgments, although subjective, were logical and consistent, adding a layer of scientific validity to the process. Aggregating judgments using the geometric mean, rather than a simple arithmetic mean, guaranteed a more balanced consensus that mitigates the impact of extreme opinions held by a single expert.

In short, the discussion of these results goes beyond simply listing an ordered list. It reveals a management philosophy for the public sector: to transform administrative processes, perceptions must first be transformed and resources secured. Only then can technology and strategy fulfill their true purpose.

5. Conclusions

The rigorous application of the NAHP method has allowed us to establish a clear and robust hierarchy of criteria that should be prioritized when implementing improvements in the university's administrative processes. The consolidated analysis of the four experts' opinions reveals that human and economic factors are the most critical.

Staff Resistance to Change (CI2) emerges as the most important factor, with a weight of **17.51%** . This underscores that, beyond technology or process redesign, the success of any improvement initiative depends fundamentally on the acceptance and collaboration of the people who will execute it. Past experiences and organizational culture are decisive, and any project must include a solid change management strategy.

In second and third place are **Implementation Cost (CI1)** at **17.02%** and **Resource Availability (CI5)** at **16.69%** . These results reflect the reality of public institutions, where budgetary constraints and resource allocation are decisive factors. Financial viability and the installed capacity to support improvements are primary concerns that must be addressed from the outset.

Factors such as **Impact on Business Continuity (CI4)** and **End-User Satisfaction (CI7)** occupy an intermediate position, indicating that, while important, they are perceived as manageable consequences

if the main factors (personnel, cost, and resources) are properly managed. Finally, **Technical Complexity (CI3)** is the least important criterion, suggesting that technological challenges are considered surmountable if the budget, resources, and, above all, the personnel willing to adopt the new tools are available.

In conclusion, this integrated BPM and NAHP framework proves to be an effective tool for strategic decision-making in highly uncertain environments. It provides quantitative prioritization that goes beyond intuition, allowing managers to focus their efforts and resources on the factors that will truly determine the success of administrative optimization projects.

References

- [1] Harmon, P. Business Process Change: A Guide for Business Managers and BPM and Six Sigma Professionals. In *Business Process Change*, 3rd ed.; Morgan Kaufmann: Boston, MA, USA, 2014; pp. 1–21, doi:10.1016/B978-0-12-800387-9.00001-3.
- [2] Milani, F.; Kubrak, K.; Nava, J. Strategic Business Process Redesign in the Digital Era: A Framework. *Data & Knowledge Engineering* 2024, 154, 102367, doi:10.1016/j.datak.2024.102367.
- [3] Saaty, T.L. Decision Making with the Analytic Hierarchy Process. *International Journal of Services Sciences* 2008, 1, 83–98, doi:10.1504/IJSSCI.2008.017590.
- [4] Celik, A.; Dogan, O. Optimizing Travel Requests with Process Simulation Analysis. *Computers & Industrial Engineering* 2024, 196, 110487, doi:10.1016/j.cie.2024.110487.
- [5] Gonçalves, L.; Moura, A.; Alvelos, H. Continuous Improvement Through Back-Office Process Automation: A Case Study on Standardized Work Documentation. *Procedia Computer Science* 2025, 253, 1185–1194, doi:10.1016/j.procs.2025.01.180.
- [6] dos Santos, A.; Rocha Loures, E.; Portela Santos, E. Application of PM2 Methodology in Assembly Process Analysis. *Procedia CIRP* 2025, 132, 159–164, doi:10.1016/j.procir.2025.01.027.
- [7] Antunes, P.; Tate, M. 'What's Going On' with BizDevOps: A Qualitative Review of BizDevOps Practice. *Computers in Industry* 2024, 157–158, 104081, doi:10.1016/j.compind.2024.104081.
- [8] El Kassis, M.; Bocciarelli, P.; Trouset, F.; Daclin, N.; D'Ambrogio, A.; Zacharewicz, G. An automated HLA-based approach for interoperable simulation of collaborative business processes. *Simulation Modelling Practice and Theory* 2024, 135, 102977, doi:10.1016/j.simpat.2024.102977.
- [9] Yu, J.; Xu, Y.; Zhou, J.; Chen, W. Digital transformation, total factor productivity, and enterprise innovation investment. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge* 2024, 9, 100487, doi:10.1016/j.jik.2024.100487.
- [10] Wang, Z.; Veldman, J.; Teunter, R. Process improvement under the reference price effect. *European Journal of Operational Research* 2025, 322, 937–948, doi:10.1016/j.ejor.2024.10.037.
- [11] Yin, J.; Qiu, A.; Fang, L.; Wang, N.; Dong, C.; Ge, S. STGNN: A novel spatio-temporal graph neural network for predicting complex business process performance under multi-event parallelism. *Expert Systems with Applications* 2025, 291, 128391, doi:10.1016/j.eswa.2025.128391.
- [12] Uyar, H.; Karvelas, I.; Rizou, S.; Fountas, S. Data value creation in agriculture: A review. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 2024, 227, 109602, doi:10.1016/j.compag.2024.109602.
- [13] Kahraman, C.; Oztaysi, B.; Cevik Onar, S. Single-valued and interval neutrosophic AHP methods: Analyzing the performance of outsourcing law firms. *Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems* 2020, 38, 749–759, doi:10.3233/JIFS-179831.
- [14] El-Douh, A. Health sustainability assessment using neutrosophic MCDM methodology: COVID-19 case study. *Sustainable Machine Intelligence Journal* 2023, 3, 1–10.
- [15] Karasan, A.; Ilbahar, E.; Cebi, S.; Kahraman, C. Customer-oriented product design using an integrated neutrosophic AHP, DEMATEL and QFD methodology. *Applied Soft Computing* 2022, 118, 108445, doi:10.1016/j.asoc.2022.108445.
- [16] Sahmutoglu, I.; Taskin, A.; Ayyildiz, E. Risk assessment methodology in assembly areas for post-flood evacuation using integrated neutrosophic AHP-CODAS. *Natural Hazards* 2023, 116, 1071–1103, doi:10.1007/s11069-022-05740-1.
- [17] Yu, D.; Kou, G.; Xu, Z.; Shi, S. An analysis of the evolution of AHP research collaboration: 1982–2018. *International Journal of Information Technology & Decision Making* 2021, 20, 7–36, doi:10.1142/S021962202150001X.

- [18] Dhouib, S. Optimization of the traveling salesman problem in a single-valued triangular neutrosophic number using the dhouib-matrix-TSP1 heuristic. *International Journal of Engineering* 2021, 34, 2642–2647, doi:10.5829/ije.2021.34.11b.18.
- [19] Silega, N.F.; Gil, G.A.; Mena, I.L.; Cruz, K.E. Application of the Iadov Neutrosophic Technique to Evaluate an MDD-Based Approach to Support Software Design. *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science* 2022, 19, 80–86, doi:10.54216/IJNS.190207.

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